

SELECTING AND PREPARING THE LAND FOR GROWING MULBERRY SEEDLINGS

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Roziyeva Mohinur

PhD student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Khaknazarova Umida

Master degree of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Ochilova Mumtozbeginim

Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University

Annotation: *Seedlings in this article can be planted in autumn or spring. In the southern regions of Uzbekistan with a moderate climate, deep groundwater and sufficient moisture, planting of seedlings is started in the fall, with the digging of seedlings (after November 10-20, when the leaves of the seedlings fall). This work is completed when the ground freezes. In the years of warm weather, seedlings can be planted in winter in these regions.*

Key words: *mulberry, seed, seedling, seedling, seedling water, site selection, irrigation, placement, environmental factors, leaf yield, productivity, propagation, efficiency.*

Introduction. The main sources of strengthening and improvement of cocoon nutrition fund in farms are as follows: expansion of mulberry groves, transfer of mulberry seedlings to the edges of fields and roadsides and increase of leaf yield due to their good care; reducing the cost of mulberry leaves based on the rational use of fertilizers and mechanization; establishment of mulberry plantations from high-quality mulberry cuttings and fertile seedlings grown by grafting is of great importance in improving the quality of leaves..

The area where seedlings grown from seeds are transplanted is called a nursery. After the seedlings are planted in the nursery, they are given a tall, branchy shape within two years. After that, they officially become two-year-old trees. Later they are planted in hedgerows, ditches, roadsides and field borders. These are used as food for silkworms, and the seed mother plants are established.

The goal of creating a nursery is to grow as much as possible from a unit of land, including at least 50% of the total number of hybrid standard seedlings and grafted seedlings. The tap roots of seedlings planted in the nursery are cut, and many lateral and lateral roots are formed. When such

seedlings are transferred to a special container, they turn green quickly and well. As a result of grafting fertile mulberries to them, quality grafted seedlings are grown.

Well-cultivated soil has accumulated a lot of moisture and nutrients in it, and there are few weeds in such soil. As a result of good processing, the soil in the layer where the root of the seedling grows becomes soft, granular and fertile.

Lands free from weeds or leguminous plants are best for a nursery. In such lands, 10-35% more nutrients (nitrogen) accumulate compared to the land planted with inter-row crops.

According to M.Muhamadjonov (1962), in the conditions of Tashkent region, three-year-old alfalfa can accumulate 300-400 kg of nitrogen and 10-12 tons of organic matter per area. Alfalfa is also important in reducing soil salinity..

Kh.Ubaykhujaev's experiment on mulberry-alfalfa rotation shows that when mulberry seedlings are planted in the land freed from inter-row crops (potatoes), the two-year-old first variety seedlings produced are 61%, and 90% in the land where the three-year-old alfalfa is planted. reached, that is, 23,000 more seedlings of the first variety were grown in each area of the second field than in the first.

The three-year-old bedopa intended for the nursery is plowed in autumn at a depth of -30-35 cm with a plow. In order to prevent regrowth of alfalfa on plowed land, two to three weeks before autumn plowing, the alfalfa is plowed to a depth of 7-8 cm with the plow shown below, and alfalfa roots are cut.

If the seedlings are planted in the nursery in the fall, the field is plowed and fertilized one to one and a half months before planting, and mulched one to two days before planting. Before planting a nursery on plowed land in the fall, the land is fertilized and plowed before planting.

PLS-5-25 A garden plug-lushchilnik, LBD-4,5, for plowing the land and removing weeds, installed on the tractor DT-75, T-74, T-40 "Belarus", T-54 V, T-70 C a marked harrow is used. The plantation area is plowed with the PL-5-35 plow attached to the T-150, T-4 tractor and the PLN-5-35 plow attached to the T-4 A, T-150, T-150K, DT-75 tractor.

Seedlings can be planted in autumn or spring. In the southern regions of Uzbekistan with a moderate climate, deep groundwater and sufficient moisture, planting of seedlings is started in the fall, with the digging of seedlings (after November 10-20, when the leaves of the seedlings fall). This

work is completed when the ground freezes. In the years of warm weather, seedlings can be planted in winter in these regions.

Seedlings are planted when the ground ice melts and the soil loosens. Planting is completed when the plant begins to bud (at the end of March or beginning of April). In the northern regions, where there are severe frosts and little snow in winter (Khorazm, Karakalpakstan Autonomous Republic and Bukhara and Khorezm Regions), it is better to plant seedlings in a greenhouse.

In general, seedlings should be watered consecutively regardless of which season they are planted. Then the roots stick well to the soil, and there is no air around them, otherwise, the cold temperature entering through the gap will freeze the roots.

The process of soaking mulberry seedlings that have sprouted from their seeds

In the southern and central regions, seedlings planted in autumn grow better than those planted in spring. For example, according to the results of inspection carried out at the experimental farm of the Tashkent Agricultural Institute, the height of seedlings planted on November 20 reached 190-195 cm on average in one season. The height of seedlings planted in Koklam (March 25) was only 160-165 cm. In the regions of the central region, when seedlings are planted in the fall, there is enough moisture in the soil due to precipitation, and the roots injured during transplanting will germinate in the autumn itself, and partially produce new roots when the weather is warm. In early planting, the roots of such seedlings first begin to grow, providing nutrients to young branches.

It is better to plant mulberry seedlings in the autumn in regions with a suitable climate, taking into account that all farms are very busy with

planting other crops in Koklam, some years the soil is late or, on the contrary, there is little rain, and the weather suddenly warms up.

Seedlings can be dug up after leaf shedding in autumn, and since this work extends into late autumn and even winter, in most districts planting them is carried out at night.

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